

Skills 4 eosc

D5.5 FAIR and RDM training modules for open collections

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable presents a description of the training modules and materials designed to support trainers and collection curators provide or acquire the skills required to make their digital collections open and FAIR. The deliverable also presents the methodology and collaborative approach followed to develop the materials.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
CARE	Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics
DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums,
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
NHMW	Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (EN: Natural History Museum Vienna)
OS	Open Science
PIDs	Persistent Identifiers
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management

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1 Executive summary

The increasing demand for accessible, accurate, and reusable digital information has highlighted significant challenges in collection curation in GLAM institutions (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums). Digital collections curation involves digitising collections¹, ensuring their long-term preservation, and facilitating their accessibility for research, industry, and other sectors. Digital Collections Curators², who play a vital role in this process, must possess key Open Science (OS) and Research Data Management (RDM) skills, including applying FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics) principles, supporting Open Access publishing, and managing data governance. However, gaps persist in defining the roles of Digital Collections Curators, limited specialized training, and insufficient awareness of these principles, which hinder effective data curation and the adoption of best practices across sectors.

To address these challenges, the Skills4EOSC WP5 Task 5.5 has developed the "Digital Collections Curator" training program, which equips professionals with the necessary OS and RDM skills. This training is aimed at trainers preparing courses on digital curation and can also be used for self-learning by data stewards and professionals in related roles. By collaborating with the digital curation community and performing a pilot training, the project identified existing and missing resources and integrated feedback to create a comprehensive learning path. The resulting training materials, which

¹ The training program presented here focuses on the challenges and future of object digitisation (*i.e.*, conversion of physical objects into a digital form) for Digital Collections Curators, and does not take into account born-digital objects (*i.e.*, digital objects that have no physical counterpart per se).

² Referring to the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS, see Appendix 1), "A Digital Collections Curator supports digitisation of collections and works with others to ensure the long-term preservation and reusability of digital collections. They advise and train researchers and other GLAM staff on policy, guidelines, data management plans, institutional infrastructure and data management tools related to digital collections. They provide support in planning and implementing the FAIR and decolonisation principles in data sharing practices. Associated job titles are: Data Steward, Data Librarian, Research Data Management Specialist, Research Data Manager, Research Data Management Consultant, Reproducibility Librarian, Data Manager, Data Curator." (p. 2)

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will be further complemented in 2025 H1, serve as a foundational resource to bridge the current gaps in digital curation expertise, ensuring that digital collections are managed, preserved, and made accessible in line with evolving needs.

2 Introduction

2.1 OS skills for digital collections curation

The increasing demand for accessible, accurate, and usable digital information across research, industry, and consumer sectors has revealed limitations and missed opportunities in science, business, and government, due to the underdeveloped and *ad hoc* nature of digital curation. Additionally, there is growing pressure for transparency and openness in various societal sectors, highlighting an urgent need for policies, services, technologies, and expertise in digital curation (The National Research Council, 2015).

Data stewards provide expertise in RDM, data governance, ethics, and information security, including risk assessment and mitigation. Their role also extends to developing training, advising on sustainable funding, fostering collaboration, and bridging stakeholder needs. Digital collections curation, a type of data stewardship, additionally involves digitising collections and ensuring their long-term preservation and usability through digitalisation. In this context, digitising refers to a process of converting a physical object into a digital form whereas digitalisation involves the use of digital technologies for transforming processes. Digital collections curation also includes training and guidance for researchers and GLAM professionals on policies, standards, data management strategies, and tools, specific for digital collections.

OS skills are critical for Digital Collections Curators, as they enable the effective curation, sharing, and reuse of research data and digital objects while advancing methodological innovation. These skills include applying FAIR and CARE principles, incorporating decolonisation strategies into data sharing strategies, supporting Open Access publishing, and ensuring data preservation. Regarding the implementation of decolonisation strategies, it has to be emphasised that settler-colonial approaches to research and data collection often exploit and misrepresent Indigenous knowledge, failing to acknowledge the rights and responsibilities Indigenous peoples hold over

their data (Jennings et al., 2023). This leads to data that is unreliable, difficult to access, and insufficient for informed decision-making. The CARE principles, which complement the FAIR principles³, are essential in addressing this issue by prioritizing the protection of Indigenous rights in light of increasing OS efforts. Extractive data practices and open data systems cause conflicts over sensitive Indigenous knowledge, particularly when large-scale datasets combine diverse sources, erasing the original context and intent of the data. To support Indigenous data governance, researchers must incorporate Indigenous rights, interests, and expectations into the development of information infrastructures. Applying the CARE principles ultimately fosters greater recognition of the collective rights Indigenous communities assert over their data and contributes to a just and responsible use of OS principles. By employing critical thinking, creativity, and cultural competence, data stewards align digital collections curation with ethical, legal, and social standards while contributing to the broader goals of OS. These competencies highlight the essential role of OS skills in ensuring the long-term value and accessibility of digital collections. (Whyte et al., 2023).

2.2 Challenges in digital collections curation

Current gaps and challenges in digital collections curation are multifaceted. One major issue is the lack of consensus on the roles, responsibilities, and skills of data stewards working on collections, with no established formal profiles outlining the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities, which leads to confusion and hampers effective data stewardship (Jetten, 2019; as cited in Wildgaard & Rantasaari, 2022). Additionally, there is insufficient or hard-to-find specialised education and training, which hinders capacity building and effective RDM essential for OS (Jetten et al., 2021). The latter is particularly relevant, taking into account that GLAM personnel who are not specialized in digital transformation are often the same ones involved in the creation and/or co-creation of digital assets with minimal scope and support

³ Applying the FAIR principles alone has the potential to neglect Indigenous rights.

(Maye et al., 2017). Finally, data stewards must be equipped to meet the specific needs of researchers within various project contexts, which requires ongoing adaptation and skill development (Wildgaard & Rantasaari, 2022).

Furthermore, there is also limited awareness among researchers regarding FAIR RDM and OS principles, which affects the adoption of these practices (Mystakopoulos et al., 2024). A further challenge is the lack of national and international coherent RDM practices, which results in low-quality data that hampers research progress and incurs additional costs (Wildgaard & Rantasaari, 2022). Many research datasets are not linked to publications, which limits their reuse and verification. Furthermore, achieving consistent international coordination and alignment is critical to developing coherent training programs and a unified human resources policy (Jetten et al., 2021). To address these issues, collaboration is needed across disciplines to establish common standards for documenting data, ensuring metadata is FAIR, and improving infrastructure for data curation and sharing (Wildgaard & Rantasaari, 2022).

All in all, there is a need for more effective training in ensuring data interoperability, reusability, and the management of ethical and legal concerns, particularly regarding sensitive data, contributing to the development of an institution’s mission in regard of OS (Mystakopoulos et al., 2024).

2.3 Filling the gaps through the Skills4EOSC “Digital Collections Curator” training

To effectively address these challenges and meet the growing demand for skilled professionals, it is essential to focus on equipping Digital Collections Curators with the necessary competencies in OS and RDM.

This deliverable and the associated training materials are the main output of Skills4EOSC Task 5.5 “OS and RDM skills for Open Scientific Collections”. The aim is to provide a learning path with associated learning materials and guidance that addresses the OS and RDM skills identified as MVS for the role

of Digital Collections Curators (see Appendix 1). The main target of the course are trainers preparing courses on this topic, although the resources could also be used for self-learning by Digital Collections Curators or other professionals in related roles.

The method followed to prepare the materials focuses on the reuse of available resources where possible. To that end, collaboration with the digital curation community was sought to identify and describe the resources they have already developed and to collect additional insights that can help trainers understand how and when to use the resources in their courses. A pilot event (which will inform the design of the actual train-of-trainers event in May 2025, see 6 Next steps) was then run on the 24th of September 2024 to present a sample of the materials and receive feedback from the community.

The resulting training material made here available, therefore, serves as a crucial foundation for developing the relevant skills, empowering curators to bridge the gap between current limitations and the evolving needs in digital curation across multiple sectors.

3 Methodology

3.1 Introduction

We started the process with a workshop with the Austrian GLAM community in Vienna (April 2024) to gather insights from collection professionals on the role of Digital Collections Curator and the skills it requires. Based on the information collected during the workshop and additional desk research, the MVS for the role were defined and a learning path to acquire those skills was designed. With the aim to reuse available materials where possible, we contacted experts from different types of organisations in the GLAM sector (i.e. libraries, archives, museums and botanical gardens) who had created resources that we identified as relevant for the learning path. We received positive feedback from the community and significant interest in the MVS and learning path. Resultantly, a number of experts agreed to present their training resources at a pilot event, which was organised in September 2024 to present the learning path and a taster of training materials. The collection of available training materials are available through Zenodo (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14415696](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14415696)).

3.2 Workshop with Austrian GLAM community

On 17th of April, 2024, a half-day workshop on "Digital Data Curators"⁴ in museums and collections was held at the Natural History Museum Vienna (NHMW). The event, a collaboration between the NHMW and the Austrian Museums Association ([Museumsbund Österreich](https://www.museumsbund.at/))⁵, aimed to discuss the role and requirements of Digital Data Curators in the digital transformation of museums and collections.

⁴ At the time the workshop was designed, the role name was still under discussion. The need for a stronger focus on collection aspects in the MVS and naming the role as 'Digital Collections Curator' was also an important outcome of the event and the resulting considerations.

⁵ <https://www.museumsbund.at/>

A total of 91 individuals from 35 different institutions took part in the workshop. Figure 1 illustrates the types of collections in which the participants are working.⁶

Figure 1: Number of participants and types of collections in which they are working

The workshop targeted mainly collection curators from Austrian GLAM institutions who are engaged in or interested in FAIRification of collection data.⁷ However, as Figure 1 shows, participants from other sectors that could benefit from the Open Collection data also demonstrated a keen interest in the discussion and networking opportunities (e.g. participants from institutions in the fields of research, education and science communication,

⁶ The diagram shows which category the collections in which the participants are employed fall into, rather than the institution. The focus on the collection level is necessary in the context of digital collections curation since large institutions, such as universities or museums, may manage various types of collections, each of which requires a specific skillset. Therefore, for example, the collections of a museum library are counted as a library in the Figure 1 and not as a museum.

⁷ The high number of participants from museum's collections is due to the significant number of internal participants from the NHMW. Twenty-eight participants are NHMW employees, two of whom are librarians and one of whom is an archivist.

that do not have their own collections). More information about the participants in regards of their career profiles, functions and experience in data stewardship can be found in the file "[PreliminarySurveyResults_DigitalCollectionCuratorWS.pptx](#)" available in Zenodo with the training materials (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14415696](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14415696)).

3.2.1 Workshop outline

The agenda started with a panel discussion of experts, who explored various aspects of data management and digitisation in the cultural sector.

The workshop focused on four main topics that were worked out in group sessions:

- Handling data in the cultural heritage sector
- Data management in practice
- OS
- Fundamentals of data management

Participants were divided into groups, each focusing on the discussion of two of the above topics and developing key aspects on the skills, training, and changes needed for the position of Data Curator/Data Steward. The discussion results were altogether collected in pin boards. The formation of new groups followed, each focusing on the needs of specific collection objects. The final summary of the pin boards and the discussion of the key requirements for the position of Data Curator/Data Steward marked the highlight of the workshop and emphasized its value for the future development of Digital Data Curatorship.

3.2.2 Main outcomes

The discussions highlighted the range of competencies that Digital Data Curators must possess today in order to fully realize the potential of digital collections while preserving the objects.

A central aspect resulting from the workshop discussion was the importance of communication skills and the ability to mediate as Digital Data Curators. In addition to tact and social competence, the advocating for good metadata practice and the ability to collaborate across disciplines were emphasized. Likewise, data management competence and an overview of legal fundamentals of the digital heritage domain were considered important. In addition to these key competences, discipline-specific knowledge and a basic understanding of the collection objects were seen as essential. Only in this way can quality standards be maintained during digitisation, digitalisation, and cataloguing. Other topics discussed at the workshop included sustainability (including "Green IT"), as well as long-term archiving and data transformation. The management of intersections between different systems and stakeholders was also addressed. The participants agreed that while training and further education are important, the majority of knowledge is acquired through daily practice, which presupposes institutions' continuous engagement in the matter. Nevertheless, it was emphasized that permanent positions and sufficient financial resources are essential for advancing the sustainable digitisation of collections. Overall, the workshop provided a platform for exchange and networking among professionals from museums, collections, and related fields.

3.3 Development of the MVS

A MVS for the role of 'Digital Collections Curator' was developed (see Appendix 1). In keeping with the format developed elsewhere in the project, the MVS aimed to highlight essential skills required for this role, alongside the activities and expected outcomes that provide the context for acquiring skills.

The MVS was adapted from an existing one for Data Stewards⁸. This was on the basis that the Data Steward role was seen as similar to that needed by

⁸ Whyte, A., & Green, D. (2024). Data Steward: Minimum Viable Skills Profile. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006764>

museums, libraries and archives, with the difference that in the latter the role focuses on making FAIR and open for research digital objects that are derived from collections along with datasets derived from these digital objects. Outcomes from the workshop described in section 3.2 above were the main source used to adapt the Data Steward MVS, together with additional reference sources relating to the museum, library, and archive collections context.

The draft was developed iteratively by the task group, and annotated using terms selected from a subset of the [ESCO](#)⁹ ontology identified by Skills4EOSC WP2. The resulting MVS has been shared with members of the [RDA Collections as Data Interest Group](#)¹⁰ for comment, and the final draft will be published in the updated version of the Skills4EOSC Catalogue of MVS.

3.4 Learning path

Once the required MVS for Digital Collections Curators were defined, we started the development of a learning path addressing the required skills.

We decided that each module should combine introductory descriptions of the key concepts and case studies from museums, libraries and archives to highlight the different solutions that have worked for different organisations and domains. We also looked to build on the resources that were already available as much as possible and to engage professionals from the GLAM the community to get their views and insights.

The modules that form the learning path are described in Section 4.

3.5 Pilot event

A pilot event was run on the 24th of September 2024 to present the learning path structure and learning objectives, provide a sample of the content, and

⁹ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/collections-as-data-ig/work-statement/>

receive feedback from the community.¹¹ A detailed report of the event is available in MS5.5 report “Piloted training modules for Open Collections”.¹²

Experts from the GLAM community were contacted and engaged in the creation of case studies to be included in the learning resources. Where possible, the contributors presented their cases studies in the pilot and participated in the discussions.

The feedback on the learning objectives and learning path was positive and participants appreciated the opportunity to discuss the topics with other experts in the community. Participants valued the inclusion of general introductions to the key topics and the cross-domain exchange provided by the case studies, but suggested including more practical aspects (e.g. such as "how to implement the FAIR principles" or "what to do to solve licensing issues") and a long-term perspective (e.g. “what changes to expect in the field in the next 10 years”).

3.6 Publication of the training resources

The training materials (*i.e.*, course slides in PPTX format from internal and external contributors) were uploaded to the Zenodo Skills4EOSC Community as a Lesson slideset and is available under the DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14415696](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14415696).

¹¹ The order of the modules had to be changed (swapping Modules 3 and 4) in the pilot to accommodate the different time zones of collaborators.

¹² Available in Zenodo under DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14507092](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14507092)

4 Learning path

The learning path is structured in four modules

- Module 1: Planning and strategy
- Module 2: Data digitisation, processing and preservation
- Module 3: Sharing: making library, archive & museum collections FAIR
- Module 4: Data governance - legal and ethical considerations

Each module consists of introductory lessons (marked in blue in Table 1), case studies (marked in red) and discussion topics (marked in green). The case studies are meant to present challenges encountered and solutions applied in different types of GLAM organisations. The learning path in Table 1, has some slots available for additional case studies, which are marked with [*] and is outlined as a training session template (*i.e.*, including duration and breaks). It is expected that some of these additional case studies could be used to address the suggestion of the pilot participants to include a long-term view, with experts describing the developments that they see in their domains in the near and medium term.

One of the suggestions from the pilot participants was to add some more practical content to the training materials. Currently, there is a practical exercise only in module 4, but the addition of further exercises will be taken into consideration in the lessons that are still to be developed.

Additionally, because the training-of-trainers should not only provide participants with content and materials to deliver in the actual training but also with skills relevant for the training itself, further instructional materials - instructional design training - that were produced in WP3 within Skills4EOSC will be adapted and made available for this purpose.

Table 1: Learning path modules and content

	Title	Duration
Module 1	Planning and strategy Learning objectives: Gain knowledge of principles relating to FAIR data, OS, and Open Collections, the policy and legal contexts to these principles, and strategies for implementing them in diverse GLAM institutions and domains. This includes understanding of training requirements to build the essential skills for Open Collections practices, policies and procedures, including knowledge/awareness of relevant software development.	1 half day (150min)
	Lesson 1.1. Preparing for FAIR and open collections that meet community interests	20
	Lesson 1.2. Developing essential skills for managing research data derived from collections	25
	<i>Break</i>	20
	Case study 1.1. DMP for Meise Botanic Garden (by Mathias Dillen)	10
	[*] Other institutional issues and case studies (libraries)	10
	[*] Other institutional issues and case studies (archives or museums)	10
	Q&A	10
	Group discussion: challenges in each sector	35
	Summary and conclusions	15
Module 2	Data digitisation, processing and preservation Learning objectives: Knowledge and understanding of practical steps to manage Collections as Data, to apply OS principles to data derived from digital collections. This includes abilities to establish and maintain good data management practices relevant	1 half day (150min)

	to open digital collections, and to ensure data quality and long-term preservation by performing data transformation and migration, establishing processes for information security, risk management, version control, and documentation. It also includes the ability to promote the value of good data management among data producers and users, researchers, support services colleagues, and relevant committees.	
	Lesson 2.1. RDM cycle for open collections	20
	Lesson 2.2. Curation workflows to manage digital GLAM collections	25
	<i>Break</i>	20
	Case study 2.1. Libraries: Checklist for collections as data (by Gustavo Candela)	10
	Case study 2.2. Museums: scientific object base collections (by Heimo Rainer)	10
	[*] Other case studies - Archives (e.g. digitising biodiversity collections (or) audio-visual materials - challenges & solutions)	10
	Q&A	10
	Group discussion – success factors each object type	35
	Summary and conclusions	10
Module 3	<p>Sharing: making library, archive & museum collections FAIR</p> <p>Learning objectives: Ability to apply FAIR principles to collections, and to other digital objects they interoperate with, including software. This includes the capability to apply standards, ontologies, infrastructure and tools for (meta)data publishing and sharing, and for managing the associated workflows. It also includes discussions about the</p>	1 half day (150min)

	capability to provide open access to collections and the challenges of considering the concept of paradata in digital collections curation.	
	Lesson 3.1. Applying FAIR principles to collections	20
	[*] Lesson 3.2. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), documentation, and collections metadata	25
	<i>Break</i>	20
	Case study 3.1. FAIR implementation starts at home. Collection Data Curation and FAIR Playbook (by Sharif Islam)	10
	Case study 3.2. Libraries – Making libraries FAIR (by Donat Agosti)	10
	Case study 3.3: collections-as-[FAIR]-data in a marine science library (by Amanda Whitmire)	10
	Q&A discussion	25
	Conclusions	10
Module 4	<p>Data governance- legal and ethical considerations</p> <p>Learning objectives: Ability to establish governance processes to handle ethical and legal/ regulatory aspects of managing digital open collections in the GLAM sector. This requires understanding of processes to handle intellectual property rights, deal with personal data, and ensure the responsible reuse of digital objects, including through the decolonisation of collections. It also requires familiarity with sustainable business modelling approaches relevant to the sector, including to establish appropriate levels of resource pooling and coordination across services.</p>	1 half day (150min)
	Lesson 4.1. Introduction to legal considerations	15
	Case study 4.1. Personal data handling for historical collections (by Andreas Salmhofer)	10

Title of the Document

	Lesson 4.2. Responsible Open Science and intellectual property rights (by Teodora Konach)	15
	[*] Other case studies (e.g. Licensing challenges for collections data)	10
	Q&A, discussion	10
	<i>Break</i>	20
	Lesson 4.3. Decolonising collections	10
	Case study 4.3. Museums - DiMuse project	10
	[*] Other case studies - Libraries/archives	10
	Discussion groups: apply principles and practices to scenarios	30
	Conclusions	10

5 Training materials

The training materials consist of the results of a survey conducted during the workshop in April 2024, lessons and case studies for the four (4) training modules in PDF-formatted slides, which were used for the pilot training on September 24th, 2024.

The slideset is available in Zenodo under the DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14415696](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14415696) and the material outline is described in Table 2. The table also contains additional training materials currently under development, which will be available by May 2025 after the delivery of an official trainer-to-trainer event (see 6. Next steps).

Table 2: Outline of the training materials

	Title	Slide
Module 1: Planning and strategy	Results of the preliminary survey for the workshop on “Digital Collections Curator” in museums and collections	PreliminarySurveyResults_DigitalCollectionCuratorWS.pptx
	Introduction to Digital Collections Curator Training Pilot	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_Introduction_ModulesOutline.pptx
	Lesson 1.1. Preparing for FAIR and open collections that meet community interests	<i>Under development</i>
	Case study 1.1. The Meise Botanic Garden Herbarium Data Management Plan (by Mathias Dillen)	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_M1_1.1_CaseStudy.pptx
	Lesson 1.2. Developing essential skills for managing research data derived from collections (by Angus Whyte)	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_M1_1.2_Lesson.pptx

Module 2 : Data digitisation, processing and preservation	Lesson 2.1. RDM cycle for Open Collections	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_M2_2.1_Lesson.pptx
	Case study 2.1. A checklist to publish Collections as Data: a Labs approach (by Gustavo Candela)	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_M2_2.1_CaseStudy.pptx
	Lesson 2.2. Curation workflows to manage digital GLAM collections	<i>Under development</i>
	Case study 2.2. Scientific object base collections (by Heimo Rainer)	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_M2_2.2_CaseStudy.pptx
Module 3: Sharing: making library, archive & museum collections FAIR	Lesson 3.1. Applying FAIR principles to collections	<i>Under development</i>
	Case study 3.1. FAIR implementation at home: Collection Data Curation and FAIR Playbook (by Sharif Islam)	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_M3_3.1_CaseStudy.pptx
	Lesson 3.2. PIDS, documentation, and collections metadata	<i>Under development</i>
	Case study 3.2. Making Libraries FAIR (by Donat Agosti)	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_M3_3.2_CaseStudy.pptx
	Case study 3.3. Collections-as-[FAIR]-data in a marine science library (by Amanda Whitmire)	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_M3_3.3_CaseStudy.pptx
Module 4: Data governance-legal and ethical considerations	Lesson 4.1. Introduction to legal considerations	<i>Under development</i>
	Case study 4.1. Mauthausen memorial: Personal data handling for historical collections	DigitalCollectionCurator-PilotTraining_M4_4.1_CaseStudy.pptx
	Lesson 4.2. Responsible Open Science and	DigitalCollectionCurator-

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intellectual property rights (by Teodora Konach)	PilotTraining_M4_4.2_Lesson.pptx
Lesson 4.3. Decolonising collections (by Angus Whyte)	DigitalCollectionCurator- PilotTraining_M4_4.3_Lesson.pptx

6 Next steps

Additional materials, like introductory lessons (see Table 2), information on publicly available collections digitisation guidelines and further case studies, will be incorporated as additional training resources upon the delivery of the hybrid (online and in-person) train-the trainer session in 2025 H1.

We intend to engage the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres and relevant infrastructures in a conversation about the outcomes of this task and how can be incorporated into their work. To that end, we will participate in the Skills4EOSC in-person workshop on preparing thematic recommendations for OS and RDM training that will take place in Pisa on 26th and 27th of February 2025 with the participation of Competence Centres representatives. The training will be held in May 2025 in a hybrid format at the NHMW.

Participation in a [DiSSCo](#)¹³ Workshop end of January about actionable data management plans and domain specific Thesaurus construction and reuse based on FAIR principles and linked data concepts is planned. Secondly, characterisation and description of collections based on domain specific data standards [Latimer Core](#)¹⁴.

¹³ Distributed System of Scientific Collections <https://www.dissco.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://lrc.tdwg.org/>

7 References

No	Description/Link
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R2	Jetten, M., Grootveld, M., Mordant, A., Jansen, M., Bloemers, M., Miedema, M., & Van Gelder, C. W. G. (2021). Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship (1.1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4623713
R3	Jetten, M. (2019). Professionalizing data stewardship in the RDA community. RDA. https://www.rd-alliance.org/professionalizing-data-stewardship-rda-community (as cited in Wildgaard & Rantasaari, 2022, R7).
R4	Maye, L. A., Bouchard, D., Avram, G. & Ciolfi, L. (2017). Supporting Cultural Heritage Professionals Adopting and Shaping Interactive Technologies in Museums. <i>Proceedings of the 2017 Conference on Designing Interactive Systems, Edinburgh, UK, 10–14 June 2017</i> ; pp. 221–232. https://doi.org/10.1145/3064663.3064753
R5	Mystakopoulos, F., Avanço, K., Souyioultzoglou, I., Gingold, A., Sokolova, E., & Delmazo, C. (2024). D5.2 OS and RDM learning paths for Social Sciences and Humanities communities. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12805056
R6	National Research Council (2015). Preparing the Workforce for Digital Curation. Washington, DC: <i>The National Academies Press</i> . https://doi.org/10.17226/18590

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R7	Wildgaard, L., & Rantasaari, J. (2022). RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship - Data Stewardship Landscape Initial Report (1.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00076
R8	Whyte, A., Green, D., Avanço, K., Di Giorgio, S., Gingold, A., Horton, L., Koteska, B., Kyprianou, K., Prnjat, O., Rauste, P., Schirru, L., Sowinski, C., Torres Ramos, G., van Leersum, N., Sharma, C., Méndez, E., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (v1.2). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101903
R9	Whyte, A., & Green, D. (2024). Data Steward: Minimum Viable Skills Profile. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006764

Appendix 1: MVS Digital Collections Curator

Introduction

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) offers a framework for describing and recognising activities and skills required for OS specialists in GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums). This MVS, for Digital Collections Curators, describes expertise required to enhance the value of GLAM sector digital collections, e.g. to the scholarly community and the public, while respecting rights and legitimate interests of all other stakeholders. This includes individuals or groups described by collections, researchers wishing to use them, and host institutions and other organisations (e.g. infrastructures, funders) involved in maintaining access.

We recognise that a variety of other job titles can also perform the curation tasks described here, e.g. Data Curator, Data Librarian or Data Manager. Expertise in digital collections curation is usually distributed among several people, drawing on internal skills and external services provided to the GLAM institution, e.g. by a Competence Centre or other provider. The appropriate distribution of expertise depends on cost and the availability of skills to meet needs. The document includes background assumptions about contextual factors that may influence these.

Digital Collections Curators play a key role in the EOSC. As practitioners and advocates of OS, and as educators and enablers of others in their organisation (especially researchers), they are likely to be both consumers and providers of services or resources.

Digital Collections Curator

A Digital Collections Curator supports digitisation of collections and works with others to ensure the long-term preservation and reusability of digital collections. They advise and train researchers and other GLAM staff on policy, guidelines, data management plans, institutional infrastructure and data management tools related to digital collections. They provide support in planning and implementing the FAIR and decolonisation principles in data sharing practices.

Associated job titles: *Data Steward, Data Librarian, Research Data Management Specialist, Research Data Manager, Research Data Management Consultant, Reproducibility Librarian, Data Manager, Data Curator.*

Essential skills and competences

Each requires understanding of the context, the processes required to perform the main activities involved, and transversal competences ('soft skills') to engage with the various stakeholders.

- Knowledge of principles relating to FAIR data, OS, and Open Collections, the policy and legal contexts to these principles, and strategies for implementing them in diverse GLAM institutions and domains. This includes understanding of training requirements to build the essential skills for Open Collections practices, policies and procedures, including knowledge/awareness of relevant software development.
- Knowledge and understanding of practical steps to manage Collections as Data, to apply OS principles to data derived from digital collections. This includes abilities to establish and maintain good data management practices relevant to open digital collections, and to ensure data quality and long-term preservation by performing data transformation and migration, establishing processes for information security, risk management, version control, and documentation. It also

includes the ability to promote the value of good data management among data producers and users, researchers, support services colleagues, and relevant committees.

- Ability to apply FAIR principles to collections, and to other digital objects they interoperate with, including software. This includes the capability to apply standards, ontologies, infrastructure and tools for (meta)data publishing and sharing, and for managing the associated workflows. It also includes the capability to provide open access to collections.
- Ability to establish governance processes to handle ethical and legal/regulatory aspects of managing digital open collections in the GLAM sector. This requires understanding of processes to handle intellectual property rights, deal with personal data, and ensure the responsible reuse of digital objects, including through the de-colonialisation of collections. It also requires familiarity with sustainable business modeling approaches relevant to the sector, including appropriate levels of resource pooling and service coordination.

Soft / transversal skills

- Ability to interact positively and productively with others, e.g. when addressing audiences, moderating discussions, or collaborating in teams and networks. This includes abilities to effect agreements, reconcile, resolve problems, and provide improvement strategies with a patient, empathetic approach.
- Exercise critical judgement, develop own assumptions, and establish a way of working based on critical thinking.
- Ability to develop innovative, novel solutions, with curiosity, openness, and a willingness to learn. This includes abilities to obtain and synthesize information to identify and explore trends, opportunities, threats (also based on intuition and creativity); and to identify alternative paths to turn ideas into action, selecting the most appropriate approach.

Title of the Document

- Direct activities and tasks, establish schedules and coordinate the activities of groups and individuals to complete objectives on time and within budget.

The table matches the above essential skills to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies, for additional information and to aid discovery of this MVS.¹⁵

Table 3: OS skills terms

Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities	Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities
Demonstrate disciplinary expertise	Teach in academic or vocational contexts
Interact professionally in research and professional environments	Core skills
Manage FAIR data	Life skills
Manage intellectual property rights	Self-management skills
Manage research data	Social and communication skills
Operate open source software	Thinking skills

¹⁵ Further information regarding the OS skills terms outlined in the Table 3 can be retrieved under the following links:

- European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology (ESCO), https://esco.ec.europa.eu/de/classification/skill_main;
- ResearchComp, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/researchcomp-european-competence-framework-researchers_en;
- terms4FAIRskills, <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/t4fs.html>

Background assumptions

Organisational context: Digital Collections Curators serve research teams and departments in institutions that are directly involved in the publication of collection objects or the production of research results, such as:

- Museums that conduct research
- Libraries and archives
- University collections
- Research infrastructures

OS mission for this role: A Digital Collections Curator works with stakeholders to establish and manage processes to generate and maintain digital data collections with their associated metadata. They also make collections usable for research, facilitate their quality assurance, and their transformation into research outputs. The role also supports informed decisions about the openness of collections and data derived from them, for re-use in line with ethical, legal and social expectations.

What results of OS does the Digital Collections Curator contribute to?

- Digital collection objects are as FAIR and open as possible and as closed as necessary.
- Opportunities for the creation of or connection to professional Open Collections networks at institutional, cross-institutional, regional, national or international level are identified.
- Relevant competence centres with a FAIR Data and Open Collections support function are effectively used according to local needs and strategies.
- Open Collections skills and practices are promoted and enhanced through the use of EOSC resources and services, including relevant Open Educational Resources (OER), where appropriate.

Title of the Document

- Collection data and other digital objects are effectively managed to ensure their suitability for archiving and sharing, and the further development of research methods appropriate to the discipline(s).

Main activities of the Digital Collections Curator

Digital Collections Curators activities include the following:

- Identifies the needs of stakeholders and contributes to the development, implementation and monitoring of institutional policies governing research data derived from collections, together with related tools and services to support them, including through contribution to (inter)national policy development. Promotes and communicates the importance of Open Collections, FAIR and decolonisation principles at all levels within the museum or collection.
- Monitors the capabilities of researchers to reuse open collections responsibly, and analyses trends in tools and methods that could improve the implementation of FAIR and CARE principles to support responsible reuse, providing advice on the use of disciplinary standards and ontologies to produce FAIR research outputs, and relevant (meta)data standards and contextual documentation to archive data for future reuse.
- Supports researchers in museums and collections to apply best practice in relation to data and/or software/code when preparing proposals to funders, implements this best practice as a regular aspect of research activity and liaises with (technical) RDM experts within and outside the institution to find effective solutions to challenges.
- Advises and supports researchers who use GLAM collections on adopting relevant data infrastructures, innovative techniques and tools to support them, including those provided by relevant (inter)national data infrastructures and tools.

Title of the Document

- Assists researchers using GLAM collections to comply with laws, regulations, and policies on legal and ethical behaviour, through liaison with institutional data protection officers, legal experts, and research ethics bodies. As a result, identifies gaps and takes action where needed to ensure ethical behaviour and awareness of the potential impact of data reuse, management and sharing on society.
- Maintains networks of colleagues involved in research data management and research support in the GLAM sector, including by co-developing and delivering training tailored to the needs of collection users and stakeholders, and by collaborating to deliver overall institutional policies and plans.

Further reference sources

No	Description/Link
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R2a	<p>Demchenko, Y., Stoy, L., Engelhardt, C., & Gaillard, V. (2021). D7.3 FAIR Competence Framework for Higher Education (Data Stewardship Professional Competence Framework). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4562089</p>
R3a	<p>Digital Preservation Coalition (2024) Example Digital Preservation Role Descriptions</p> <p>https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/prof-development/dp-competency/dp-roles</p>
R4a	<p>EMBL-EBI. (2023). Competency Hub.</p> <p>https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/framework/datasteward/1.0/competencies</p>
R5a	<p>EOSC Executive Board; Skills and Training Working Group & European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. (2021). Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science: Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group. (p. 71) [Expert]. Publications Office.</p> <p>https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065</p>
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R9a	<p>Jetten, M., Grootveld, M., Mordant, A., Jansen, M., Bloemers, M., Miedema, M., & Gelder, C. W. G. V. (2021). Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship (1.1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320504</p>
R10a	<p>Molloy, L., Gow, A., & Konstantelos, L. (2014). The DigCurV curriculum framework for digital curation in the cultural heritage sector. International Journal of Digital Curation, 9(1), 231–241. http://dx.doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v9i1.314</p>
R11a	<p>Scholtens, S., Jetten, M., Böhmer, J., Staiger, C., Slouwerhof, I., Van Der Geest, M., & Van Gelder, C. W. G. (2022). Final report: Towards FAIR data steward as profession for the lifesciences. Report of a ZonMw funded collaborative approach built on existing expertise (Version 4). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3471707</p>
R12a	<p>Semeler, A. R., Pinto, A. L., & Rozados, H. B. F. (2019). Data science in data librarianship: Core competencies of a data librarian. Journal of Librarianship and Information Science, 51(3), 771–780.</p>

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R15a	Wildgaard, L., Vlachos, E., Nondal, L., Larsen, A. V., & Svendsen, M. (2020). <i>National Coordination of Data Steward Education in Denmark: Final report to the National Forum for Research Data Management (DM Forum)</i> (Version 1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3609515